

Coumaro- α -pyrones

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Hantzsch and Zürcher (*Ber.*, 1887, **20**, 1329) obtained in extremely poor yield dimethylcoumaro- α -pyrone (I), which they called dimethylidicoumarin, by condensing one molecule of resorcinol with two molecules of acetoacetic ester in one operation in the presence of concentrated sulphuric acid.

(I)

While engaged in a study of the reactivity of the substituted phenols in the formation of coumarins by Pechman's method, the present authors noticed that resorcinol and other polyhydroxy phenols do not condense satisfactorily with two molecules of acetoacetic ester or malic acid simultaneously; but the pure hydroxycoumarins (from one molecule of each of the reactants) may be made to react under proper conditions with a second molecule of acetoacetic ester or malic acid producing coumaro- α -pyrones of Hantzsch and Zürcher type with much better yield. It has also been noticed incidentally that the hydroxycoumarins react more readily with malic acid than with acetoacetic ester (yield, 40-70%) even at the temperature of the water-bath, though the condensation of ordinary aromatic hydroxy compounds with malic acid generally requires a much higher temperature.

The monohydroxycoumarins, used for the synthesis of the coumaro- α -pyrones in this paper, have been obtained by the condensation of resorcinol and orcinol with (i) malic acid (Pechman, *Ber.*, 1884, **17**, 929; Pechman and Welsh, *Ber.*, 1894, **17**, 1646) and (ii) acetoacetic ester (Pechman and Duisberg, *Ber.*, 1883, **16**, 2119; Pechman and Cohen, *Ber.*, 18'4, **17**, 2187). Umbelliferone (from resorcinol and malic acid) gives the coumaro- α -pyrone (III) or (IV) with malic acid; while 4-methylumbelliferone

(from resorcinol and acetoacetic ester) produces (i) 4-methylcoumaro- α -pyrone with malic acid and (ii) 4:4'-dimethylcoumaro- α -pyrone with acetoacetic ester. Supposing the hydroxycoumarins derived from resorcinol to be 7-hydroxycoumarins (II) in accordance with Pechman's view (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 929), the corresponding coumaropyrones may have one of the two possible structures (III or IV).

(II)

(III)

Coumaro-7:6- α -pyrone.

or

(IV)

Coumaro-7:8- α -pyrone.

The first number following the word 'coumaro' refers to the carbon atom in the benzene nucleus to which the oxygen in the second pyrone ring is attached.

Attempt to settle between these two structures by the oxidation of the simple coumaropyrones with alkaline potassium permanganate proved unsuccessful.

Similarly two different structures are also possible for the coumaropyrones derived from orcinol, if the hydroxyl group in these hydroxycoumarins occupy the position 7; but assuming these hydroxycoumarins to be 5-hydroxycoumarins, as suggested by Dey (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1614), the coumaropyrones (V) from orcinol will admit of only one structure. Thus homoumbelliferone (from orcinol and malic acid) gives 7-methylcoumaro-5:6- α -pyrone with malic acid; while 4-methylhomoumbelliferone (from orcinol and acetoacetic ester) produces (i) 4:7-di-

methylcoumaro-5:6-*a*-pyrone with malic acid and (ii) 4:4':7-trimethylcoumaro-5:6-*a*-pyrone with acetoacetic ester.

(V)

7-Methylcoumaro-5:6-*a*-pyrone.

The hydroxycoumarin, derived from hydroquinone (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1649) could not be further condensed with acetoacetic ester or malic acid; while the attempt to prepare a hydroxycoumarin from catechol has not been successful.

The dihydroxycoumarins, derived from pyrogallol and phloroglucinol by their condensation with one molecule of acetoacetic ester or malic acid (*Pechman, loc. cit.*; *Pechman and Cohen, loc. cit.*; *Pechman and Duisberg, loc. cit.*) have also been made to react further with a second molecule of malic acid at the temperature of the water-bath, yielding monohydroxycoumaro-*a*-pyrones. Daphnetin (from pyrogallol and malic acid) and 4-methyl-daphnetin (from pyrogallol and acetoacetic ester) condense with malic acid producing respectively 8-hydroxycoumaro-7:6-*a*-pyrone and 4-methyl-8-hydroxycoumaro-7:6-*a*-pyrone (VI).

(VI)

It is remarkable that the dihydroxycoumarins, derived from pyrogallol, do not react further with acetoacetic ester, although they react readily with malic acid.

The condensation of phloroglucinol with acetoacetic ester gives a dihydroxycoumarin (VII), which with malic acid may lead to the formation of a coumaro-*a*-pyrone having any one of the following

possible structures (VIII, IX or X); but as Hantzsch and Zurcher (*loc. cit.*) have shewn that the hydroxycoumarin from phloroglucinol and acetoacetic ester by further reaction with acetoacetic ester forms a coumaro dipyrone (XI) the formation of which follows best from structures (IX) or (X) for the coumaropyrone, the structure (VIII) is therefore excluded.

The coumaro- α -pyrones, the mono-, di-, and tri-methylcoumaro- α -pyrones, the hydroxy- and the hydroxy-methylcoumaro- α -pyrones, thus synthesised, are a series of a new type of interesting compounds. They are all difficultly soluble, fine, crystalline substances with high melting points. They all dissolve in hot caustic alkali solutions, the lactone rings being broken up; and excepting those containing a free hydroxyl group, they are almost in-

soluble in ammonia, while they all remain practically unaffected by sodium carbonate and bicarbonate solutions in the cold; both the lactone rings being thus quite stable like that of coumarin itself. Excepting those coumaro- α -pyrones in which both 4 and 4' positions are substituted by methyl groups, all these coumaro- α -pyrones dissolve in hot sodium bisulphite solutions (*cf.* Dey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 123, 554). The hydroxycoumaro- α -pyrones form mono-acetyl derivatives. Qualitative tests indicate the formation of nitration and sulphonation products of those compounds. Further study of the derivatives of these new coumaro- α -pyrones is in progress.

The condensations of the hydroxycoumarins with acetone dicarboxylic acid have also led to the formation of coumaro- α -pyrone-acetic acids, which will be the subject of a future communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Coumaro-7:6 (or 7:8)- α -pyrone.—An intimate mixture of umbelliferone (4 g.) (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 929), malic acid (4 g.) and sulphuric acid (*d* 1.84, 12 c. c.) is heated on the water-bath. Effervescence soon begins and the solution assumes a deep-red colour. The solution is heated until the effervescence ceases (3-4 hours) and is then poured into powdered ice, when a red coloured precipitate is obtained. The precipitate is then filtered off, digested with ammonia to remove any unchanged umbelliferone and is crystallised from glacial acetic acid (yield, 60%). It forms reddish-yellow leaflets, m. p. 245-250°, almost insoluble in ether and chloroform; sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone and moderately soluble in hot glacial acetic acid. It is almost insoluble in ammonia and sodium carbonate solution, but soluble in hot caustic alkalis (reddish solution) without any fluorescence. (Found: C, 66.9, 67.1; H, 3.2, 3.1. $C_{12}H_6O_4$ requires C, 67.29; H, 2.8 per cent.).

7-Methylcoumaro-5:6- α -pyrone.—A solution of homoumbelliferone (3.5 g.) (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1646) and malic acid (3.5 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c. c.) is heated for about two hours on the water-bath until effervescence ceases. The method of purification of the compound is the same as in the previous case (yield, 50%). It forms greyish silky needles from glacial acetic acid, m. p. 318-320° with slight decomposition; sparingly soluble in ether, hot chloroform, benzene; moderately soluble in boiling alcohol and acetone and

almost insoluble in ammonia and sodium carbonate solution, but dissolves in hot caustic alkalis without fluorescence. (Found: C, 68.4; H, 3.7. $C_{13}H_8O_4$ requires C, 68.42; H, 3.5 per cent.)

4-Methylcoumaro-7:6 (or 7:8)-*a*-pyrone.—A solution of 4-methylumbelliferone (10 g.) (*Ber.*, 1883, 16, 2119) and malic acid (10 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (30 c. c.) is heated on the water-bath for 2–3 hours until the effervescence ceases. The method of purification of the compound is the same as in the previous cases (yield, 70%). It forms thin silky needles from a mixture of acetone and chloroform (1:3) and micro-crystalline from hot glacial acetic acid; m. p. 304.5°. It is almost insoluble in ether or benzene, sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone; moderately soluble in chloroform and very slightly soluble in hot ammonia with a yellow colouration. No fluorescence in alkaline solution. (Found: C, 68.068.2; H, 3.8, 3.9. $C_{13}H_8O_4$ requires C, 68.42; H, 3.5 per cent.)

4:7-Dimethylcoumaro-5:6-*a*-pyrone.—A mixture of 4-methylhomoumbelliferone (5 g.) (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2187), malic acid (5 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c. c.) is heated on the water-bath for about three hours until the effervescence ceases. The solution is then poured into water, the precipitate is filtered, dried, and digested with boiling absolute alcohol. The residue is finally crystallised from a mixture of acetic acid and acetic anhydride (3:1) (yield, 65%). It forms beautiful, colourless, thin, silky needles, m. p. 310–313°, difficultly soluble in the organic solvents, insoluble in ammonia, soluble in hot caustic alkalis without any fluorescence. (Found: C, 69.1; H, 4.2. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 69.42; H, 4.1 per cent.)

4:4'-Dimethylcoumaro-7:6 (or 7:8)-*a*-pyrone.—A mixture of 4-methylumbelliferone (10 g.), acetoacetic ester (10 c. c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (30 c. c.) is kept for about a week. The solution is then poured into water, the precipitate is filtered off, digested with hot ammonia to remove the unchanged 4-methylumbelliferone and is finally crystallised from a large quantity of boiling alcohol. Yield about 30%. It forms snow-white micro-crystalline unmeltable solid, almost insoluble in the ordinary organic solvents, slightly soluble in ammonia with a yellow colour, soluble in hot caustic alkalis without any fluorescence. (Found: C, 69.31; H, 4.4. $C_{14}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 69.42; H, 4.1 per cent.)

This compound is identical in properties with the dimethyl-dicoumarin of Hantzsch and Zürcher (*loc. cit.*).

4:4': 7-Trimethylcoumaro-5: 6-*a*-pyrone.—4-Methylhomoumbelliferone (15 g.), acetoacetic ester (18 c. c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (40 c. c.) are mixed together in the cold and the solution kept for several days. The solution is then poured into powdered ice, the precipitate filtered off and digested with boiling rectified spirit. The residue is finally crystallised from a large quantity of boiling alcohol. Yield not more than 15%; colourless micro-crystalline unmeltable powder, soluble with difficulty in boiling alcohol and acetone and almost insoluble in many organic solvents. (Found: C, 70·18; H, 4·9. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 70·31; H, 4·7 per cent.).

8-Hydroxycoumaro-7:6-*a*-pyrone.—A mixture of daphnetin (4 g.) (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 920), malic acid (4 g.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (9 c. c.) is heated on the water bath for 3-4 hours till the effervescence ceases. The solution is then poured into water, the precipitate filtered, dried and digested with hot absolute alcohol. The residue is then finally crystallised from pyridine, containing a few drops of water (yield, 40%). It is a greyish microcrystalline substance, very difficultly soluble in boiling alcohol, acetone and pyridine; almost insoluble in ether, benzene, and chloroform and sodium carbonate solution, soluble in ammonia and hot caustic alkalis. (Found: C, 62·35; H, 2·8. $C_{12}H_6O_5$ requires C, 62·6; H, 2·6 per cent.).

4-Methyl-8-hydroxycoumaro-7:6-*a*-pyrone.—A solution of 4-methyl-daphnetin (9·5 g.) (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2187) and malic acid (7 g.) in sulphuric acid (20 c. c.) is heated on the water-bath till the effervescence ceases. The method of purification of the compound is the same as in the previous case. It is finally crystallised from pyridine. Yield 55%. It forms almost colourless rectangular plates, very sparingly soluble in alcohol, acetone, ether, benzene and chloroform; readily soluble in pyridine, soluble in ammonia and caustic alkalis. (Found: C, 63·7; H, 3·4. $C_{13}H_8O_5$ requires C, 63·93; H, 3·28 per cent.).

The *mono-acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual manner and crytallised from a large quantity of boiling alcohol, is a greyish powder without any melting point. (Found: C, 62·7; H, 3·7. $C_{15}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 62·93; H, 3·5 per cent.).

5-Hydroxycoumaro-7:8-*a*-pyrone or 7-Hydroxycoumaro-5:6-*a*-pyrone.—A mixture of 4-methyl-5:7-dihydroxycoumarin (9·5 g.) (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 2187) and malic acid (6 g.) and sulphuric acid

(20 c. c.) is heated on the water-bath for 3-4 hours till the effervescence ceases. The solution is then poured in ice, the precipitate filtered and dissolved in ammonia. The ammoniacal solution is acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate thus obtained is crystallised from pyridine. Yield, 60% ; colourless thin silky needles, decomposing at 320° ; it is sparingly soluble in boiling alcohol, moderately soluble in pyridine, soluble in ammonia with a yellow colour. (Found: C, 64.15; H, 3.4. $C_{13}H_8O_5$ requires C, 63.93; H, 3.28 per cent.).

The *mono-acetyl* derivative, crystallised from pyridine, is a colourless micro-crystalline powder. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 3.8. $C_{15}H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 62.93; H, 3.5 per cent.).

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